

As the new academic year starts, the DDI Alliance is gearing up for a lot of activity, especially in the area of training. DDI is spreading around the world at a rapid pace, and these new developments are very exciting. You can read more in this issue about the packed agenda for DDI through the end of the calendar year.

Mary Vardigan, Director, DDI Alliance

DDI Alliance Meets in Finland

Twenty-six participants, including visitors from the Australian Social Science Data Archive (ASSDA), took part in the [DDI Expert Committee meeting](#) held May 25, 2009, in Tampere, Finland, just before the annual meeting of IASSIST.

It was a productive meeting, with many reports and updates on DDI activities. The DDI Alliance said farewell to Ken Miller of the UK Data Archive, one of the original DDI Committee members since 1995, who recently retired from his position at the UKDA. (See the photo of Ken on page 2.) The following day, a [DDI Steering Committee meeting](#) took place.

DDI 3.1 to be Published This Fall

Last spring, the Expert Committee reviewed the new DDI version 3.1 and approved it via a formal vote. The review process turned up some issues that required research to address. The new 3.1 should be published by mid-October with the following features:

Some participants in the May 2009 meeting of the DDI Alliance in Tampere, Finland. Left to right, Steve McEachern (ASSDA), Fredy Kuhn (FORS), Pilar Rey del Castillo (CIS), Stefan Kramer (Yale), Uwe Jensen (GESIS), Taina Jaaskelainen (FSD), Iris Alfredsson (SND), Wolfgang Zenk-Moeltgen (GESIS), Atle Alvheim (NSD), Dan Gillman (BLS), Gavan McCarthy (ASSDA).

- Revised URN structure
- Consistent structure for User ID, Name, Label, Description
- Addition of Local Holding Package

Note that DDI 3.1 carries invalidating changes, so applications may need to be revised to accommodate the new 3.1 schema.

DDI on the Move!

Word about DDI has been spreading this year and we have seen interest from many quarters.

In Ithaca, NY...

DDI training was held July 13-16 at Cornell University as part of the ICPSR Summer Program, with instructors Wendy Thomas (Minnesota Population Center) and Arofan Gregory (Open Data Foundation). Many thanks to Cornell representative Bill Block, who arranged for the training.

In Durban, South Africa...

Mary Vardigan, DDI Alliance Director, wrote an invited paper for the 53rd International Statistical Institute (ISI) meeting in Durban, South Africa, which took place in August. Coauthored by University of Michigan colleagues Peter Granda, Sue Ellen Hansen, Sanda Ionescu, and Felicia LeClere, the paper described a project to create a DDI 3-based relational database for metadata reuse across the data life cycle.

In Toronto, Canada...

Wendy Thomas and Arofan Gregory will hold a DDI 3 workshop for participants in the <odesi> project on September 15-17. Odesi, or Ontario Data Documentation, Extraction Service and Infrastructure Initiative,

provides researchers with access to a significant number of datasets in a Web-based data extraction system and documentation in DDI format.

In Canberra, Australia...

Wendy Thomas, Joachim Wackerow (GESIS), and Peter Granda (ICPSR) will conduct training for archivists at ASSDA and for staff of the Australian Bureau of Statistics on September 28-October 2.

In Wadern, Germany...

GESIS will offer [training in DDI 3](#) October 25-30, 2009, at [Schloss Dagstuhl](#) in Wadern, Germany, with Wendy Thomas, Arofan Gregory, and Joachim Wackerow as instructors. The following week, November 1-6, a [session on DDI 3.0 use cases](#) will be held at Dagstuhl, with the final outcome a use case literature for DDI. Papers

will be published in a journal and on the DDI Web site.

In Bonn, Germany...

The International Data Service Center (IDSC) of [IZA](#) and [GESIS](#) are joining forces to encourage DDI adoption by launching the first ever European DDI User Group Meeting, or EDDI. Arranged by Nikos Askitas (IZA) and Joachim Wackerow, EDDI 09 will take place December 4 at the IDSC of IZA in Bonn, Germany. The day before on December 3, Wendy Thomas will lead a half-day of DDI 3 training.

And Virtually!

As part of the [ICPSR Biennial Meeting of Official Representatives](#), to be held virtually on October 5-9, Mary Vardigan will present a session on Best Practice in Documentation, highlighting the use of DDI. The online event is open to all through Webinar technology.

Ken Miller, long-serving member of the DDI Alliance, enjoying the Tampere scenery. We will miss you, Ken!